

SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED DINITROPHENYLKETONES AND PHENYLACETIC ACIDS. PART VI

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2:6-Dinitro-4-iodophenyl-acetone and -acetic acid and 2-methyl-3-carbethoxy-5-amino-7-iodoindole have been prepared.

In the previous communications (Sen and Bhargava, this *Journal*, 1947, **24**, 268, 371, 403; 1948, **25**, 282, 538) the preparation of a number of halogenated dinitrophenylketones and phenylacetic acids has been described; the method employed was to condense a halogenated dinitrobenzene containing a reactive chlorine atom, with acetoacetic and malonic esters, and to submit the resulting product to hydrolysis. In this paper, this reaction has been extended to the preparation of 2:6-dinitro-4-iodophenyl-acetone and -acetic acid. The ketone has been characterised by the preparation of its phenylhydrazone; its oxime, however, could not be obtained. The reduction of 2:6-dinitro-4-iodophenylacetoacetic ester by iron powder and water yields an indole derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Iodo-2:6-dinitrophenol was obtained previously by Armstrong (*Ber.*, 1873, **6**, 650) by the iodination of 2:6-dinitrophenol, but the exact experimental details being not available, it was prepared by us in the following way.

2:6-Dinitrophenol (20.5 g.) was dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid and a finely powdered mixture of iodine (30 g.) and freshly prepared yellow mercuric oxide (13 g.) was added to it gradually, during 1½ hours. Each addition was followed by heating the solution to boiling, and shaking till the colour of the iodine was discharged. After the addition was complete, the contents of the flask were stirred mechanically for one hour and then left overnight. The acetic acid layer was then decanted off and the residual mercuric iodide extracted twice, with 10 c.c. of glacial acetic acid each time. The combined acetic acid solutions were diluted with a small amount of water and the precipitate so obtained was filtered. On recrystallisation from hot alcohol, the iododinitrophenol was obtained as dark orange-red crystals, m.p. 112.5°. A further crop of the compound was obtained by concentrating the mother-liquor, yield 20 g. (58% of theory).

2:6-Dinitro-4-iodophenylacetoacetic Ester.—The sodium derivative of acetoacetic ester was prepared as usual, from acetoacetic ester (12.5 g.) and sodium (2 g.) in anhydrous benzene (75 c. c.). After the last traces of sodium had disappeared, the flask was cooled in ice and 1-chloro-4-iodo-2:6-dinitrobenzene (13 g.) (prepared from 4-iodo-2:6-dinitrophenol by the method of Sane and Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 61) added. The contents of the flask were stirred mechanically for one hour in cold, then refluxed for 6 hours and left overnight. The mixture was then extracted with 2% caustic soda solution (300 c. c.), the extract cooled with ice and acidified with dilute nitric acid, when a red oil separated out. This was left to settle down in a refrigerator, when the greater part of the oil solidified. The supernatant liquid was then decanted off, the mixture shaken with 40 c. c. of cold alcohol and filtered. The dark reddish brown crystals

on the filter paper consisted of the dinitroiodophenylacetoacetic ester. Another crop of the ester was obtained by allowing the alcoholic filtrate to evaporate by itself, yield 14 g. (84% of theory). On recrystallisation by dissolving in hot alcohol, filtering and allowing the filtrate to evaporate slowly, the ester was obtained as very fine, pale yellow needles, m.p. 113-14°. (Found : N, 6.81. $C_{12}H_{11}O_7N_2I$ requires N, 6.61 per cent).

2:6-Dinitro-4-iodophenylacetone.—The crude 2:6-dinitro-4-iodophenylacetoacetic ester (4 g.) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (concentrated, 45 c.c.), and to this, water (21 c.c.) was added slowly, with constant stirring and without cooling. The black solution was then allowed to stand for an hour, when the evolution of carbon dioxide ceased. It was then poured over crushed ice, allowed to stand in a refrigerator overnight and filtered, when the crude ketone was obtained as an almost black crystalline mass. On recrystallisation from hot alcohol, it was obtained as light brown crystals, m.p. 138-39°, yield theoretical. (Found : N, 8.12. $C_9H_5O_2N_2I$ requires N, 8.0 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone* of the above ketone was obtained by dissolving the crude ketone (1 g.) in hot alcohol (15 c. c.) and refluxing for one hour with phenylhydrazine (1.5 c.c.). The mixture was then cooled in ice, diluted with a small quantity of water and filtered. The dark coloured residue was dissolved in boiling alcohol, filtered hot and the filtrate allowed to evaporate slowly, when the phenylhydrazone separated out. On recrystallisation from a mixture of equal quantities of alcohol and acetone, the phenylhydrazone was obtained as a brown crystalline substance, m.p. 140-42° (decomp.), yield 0.5 g. (40% of theory). (Found : N, 12.38. $C_{16}H_{13}O_4N_4I$ requires N, 12.73 per cent).

2:6-Dinitro-4-iodophenylacetic Acid.—The crude 2:6-dinitro-4-iodophenylacetoacetic ester (2 g.) was refluxed for one hour with 20% alcoholic potash (13 c.c.) to which one c. c. of water had been added. The alcohol was then distilled off, the residue cooled in ice and then acidified with hydrochloric acid. It was filtered and the dark coloured residue extracted with hot alcohol, the extract being filtered hot. The filtrate was allowed to evaporate by itself and the dark brown acid separating was purified by dissolving in sodium carbonate solution, filtering and reprecipitating with hydrochloric acid. It does not melt but gives off iodine on heating strongly, yield 1 g. (60% of theory). (Found : N, 7.66. $C_8H_5O_6N_2I$ requires N, 7.95 per cent).

2-Methyl-3-carbethoxy-5-amino-7-iodoindole.—The crude 2:6-dinitro-4-iodophenylacetoacetic ester (1.5 g.), iron powder (2.5 g.), crystalline ferrous sulphate (0.25 g.) and water (8 c.c.) were refluxed for three hours. It was then cooled with shaking in ice and filtered. The residue was extracted four times, with 10 c.c. of alcohol each time, the extract filtered hot and the filtrate allowed to evaporate by itself when 2-methyl 3-carbethoxy-5-amino-7-iodoindole separated out as colorless crystals turning dark violet immediately on exposure to air, m.p. 194-95°, yield 1.1 g. (54% of theory). (Found : N, 7.91. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_2I$ requires N, 8.14 per cent).

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